

A Spatial Assessment of eVTOLs for Emergency Medical Transport in the Brazilian Amazon

Gabriela Oliveira de Souza^{1*} (ORCID: [0000-0003-1140-6041](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1140-6041))

Evandro José da Silva¹ (ORCID: [0000-0002-7533-4369](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7533-4369))

Mauro Caetano¹ (ORCID: [0000-0002-5978-1054](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5978-1054))

¹ Departamento de Ciência e Tecnologia Aeroespacial — Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica (ITA), Divisão de Engenharia Civil, São José dos Campos, SP, Brazil.

ROR: <https://ror.org/01x81nn04>

*Corresponding author

APPENDIX A: Location of the Cities and Hospitals Analyzed

To map the medical care network, data from the National Registry of Health Facilities (CNES) were obtained through the OpenDataSUS platform (Ministry of Health of Brazil, 2024). The obtained CSV file contains information on all hospitals in Brazil, including facility identification, address, administrative nature, and installed bed capacity, with details on ICU beds (adult, pediatric, neonatal, burn, and coronary), including those available through the Unified Health System (SUS).

The dataset was filtered to include only public and philanthropic hospitals located within the Legal Amazon. For the spatial analyses conducted in this study, only hospitals with at least one adult ICU bed available through SUS were considered. Address geocoding was performed using Google Earth Pro, and the spatial accuracy of the resulting coordinates was visually verified in the platform to ensure alignment with the actual hospital locations. The georeferenced data were then exported in GeoJSON format and integrated into QGIS for further analysis. Figure A.1 displays the spatial distribution of all public and philanthropic hospitals in the Legal Amazon.

Figure A.1: Spatial distribution of public and philanthropic hospitals in the Legal Amazon (with and without adult ICU beds)

To support the spatial analysis, the selection of hospitals was based on the location of urban centers, given that medical facilities are typically concentrated in or around these areas. As a starting point, we identified the most populous municipalities in the Legal Amazon, following the procedure described in the methodology section.

From this initial list of cities, we verified the presence of hospitals with adult ICU beds available through the Unified Health System (SUS), using data obtained from the OpenDataSUS platform. Cities without qualifying hospitals were excluded from the analysis. For each remaining city, the most suitable hospital was identified and included in the reference table. In municipalities with only one eligible facility, that hospital was selected by default. In cities with multiple qualifying hospitals, we conducted additional research to identify the one best equipped for emergency and trauma care.

Table A.1 presents the selected cities, along with their geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), population size, the presence of at least one SUS-supported adult ICU, and the name of the chosen referral hospital in each location.

Table A.1 Selected municipalities in the Legal Amazon with referral hospitals offering adult ICU beds under the SUS

Name	State	Place	Longitude	Latitude	Population	SUS ICU	Reference hospital
Cruzeiro do Sul	AC	city	-72.66916	-7.63625	91888	NO	
Rio Branco	AC	city	-67.82208	-9.97654	364756	YES	HOSPITAL GERAL DE CLINICAS DE RIO BRANCO
Itacoatiara	AM	city	-58.44610	-3.14779	103598	NO	
Manacapuru	AM	city	-60.62135	-3.29968	101883	NO	
Manaus	AM	city	-59.98250	-3.13163	2063689	YES	HOSPITAL E PRONTO SOCORRO DR ARISTOTELES PLATAO B DE ARAUJO
Parintins	AM	city	-56.73193	-2.63446	96372	NO	
Macapá	AP	city	-51.05696	0.04015	442933	YES	SES AP HOSPITAL DE EMERGENCIA
Santana	AP	city	-51.17897	-0.03071	107618	NO	
Açailândia	MA	city	-47.50073	-4.95150	106550	YES	HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL DE ACAILANDIA
Bacabal	MA	city	-44.78117	-4.23181	103711	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL LAURA VASCONCELOS
Balsas	MA	city	-46.03716	-7.53214	101767	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE BALSAS
Imperatriz	MA	city	-47.47812	-5.52693	273110	YES	HMI HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL DE IMPERATRIZ
Paço do Lumiar	MA	city	-44.15920	-2.53291	145643	NO	
Santa Inês	MA	city	-45.38269	-3.66478	85014	YES	HOSPITAL MACRORREGIONAL TOMAS MARTINS
São José de Ribamar	MA	city	-44.05595	-2.56091	244579	NO	
São Luís	MA	city	-44.29639	-2.52953	1037775	YES	HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL DJALMA MARQUES SOCORRAO I
Alta Floresta	MT	city	-56.08350	-9.86985	58613	NO	
Barra do Garças	MT	city	-52.26154	-15.89160	69210	YES	HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL MILTON PESSOA MORBECK
Cáceres	MT	city	-57.68797	-16.06443	89681	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DR ANTONIO FONTES
Cuiabá	MT	city	-56.09913	-15.59867	650877	YES	HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL DE CUIABA E P S DR LEONY PALMA CARVALHO
Primavera do Leste	MT	city	-54.29939	-15.56141	85146	NO	
Rondonópolis	MT	city	-54.63971	-16.46035	244911	YES	HOSPITAL REG IRMA ELZA GIOVANELLA
Sinop	MT	city	-55.49678	-11.85770	196312	YES	HOSPITAL SANTO ANTONIO
Sorriso	MT	city	-55.72340	-12.54449	110635	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE SORRISO
Tangará da Serra	MT	city	-57.49073	-14.62139	106434	NO	
Várzea Grande	MT	city	-56.13222	-15.64582	300078	YES	METROPOLITANO HOSPITAL ESTADUAL LOUSITE FERREIRA DA SILVA
Altamira	PA	city	-52.20996	-3.20407	126279	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DA TRANSAMAZONICA

Name	State	Place	Longitude	Latitude	Population	SUS ICU	Reference hospital
Ananindeua	PA	city	-48.40166	-1.37404	478778	YES	HOSPITAL METROPOLITANO DE URGENCIA E EMERGENCIA
Barcarena	PA	city	-48.61907	-1.51079	126650	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO MATERNO INFANTIL DE BARCARENA
Belém	PA	city	-48.46825	-1.45056	1303403	YES	HPSM DR HUMBERTO MARADEI PEREIRA
Bragança	PA	city	-46.76352	-1.05743	123082	YES	HOSPITAL SANTO ANTONIO MARIA ZACCARIA
Breves	PA	city	-50.47909	-1.68036	106968	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DO MARAJO
Cametá	PA	city	-49.49789	-2.24295	134184	NO	
Castanhal	PA	city	-47.92239	-1.29270	192256	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DE CASTANHAL
Itaituba	PA	city	-55.98781	-4.26252	123314	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DO TAPAJOS ITAITUBA
Marabá	PA	city	-49.10074	-5.34628	266533	YES	HOSPITAL MUNICIPAL DE MARABA
Marituba	PA	city	-48.33615	-1.35953	111785	YES	HOSPITAL DA DIVINA PROVIDENCIA
Paragominas	PA	city	-47.35489	-2.99564	105550	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DO LESTE DO PARA
Parauapebas	PA	city	-49.89033	-6.06968	267836	YES	HOSPITAL GERAL DE PARAUAPEBAS MANOEL EVALDO BENEVIDES ALVES
Redenção	PA	city	-50.03095	-8.02993	85597	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL PUBLICO DO ARAGUAIA
Santarém	PA	city	-54.69961	-2.43849	331942	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DO BAIXO AMAZONAS DO PA DR WALDEMAR PENNA
Tucuruí	PA	city	-49.66637	-3.76633	91306	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE TUCURUI
Ariquemes	RO	city	-63.03307	-9.90765	96833	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE ARIQUEMES
Ji-Paraná	RO	city	-61.92779	-10.87781	124333	YES	HOSPITAL DR CLAUDIONOR COUTO RORIZ
Porto Velho	RO	city	-63.87354	-8.74945	406434	YES	HOSPITAL JOAO PAULO II PORTO VELHO
Vilhena	RO	city	-60.14656	-12.73685	95832	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL ADAMASTOR TEIXEIRA DE OLIVEIRA
Boa Vista	RR	city	-60.67196	2.82085	413486	YES	HOSPITAL GERAL DE RORAIMA HGR
Araguaína	TO	city	-48.20186	-7.19324	171301	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE ARAGUAINA
Gurupí	TO	city	-49.06805	-11.72794	85125	YES	HOSPITAL REGIONAL DE GURUPI
Palmas	TO	city	-48.33364	-10.18379	302692	YES	HOSPITAL GERAL DE PALMAS DR FRANCISCO AYRES